

Table S1. Clinical characteristics and laboratory levels by obesity for MGH cohort

	Overall (N=1202)	Obese^(*) (N=499)	Not Obese^(*) (N=592)	P-value^(†)
Presentation to care (PTC)				
Time from symptoms to PTC	4 (2,7)	5 (2,8)	4 (1,7)	0.005
Fever	768/1202(0.64)	344/499(0.69)	359/592(0.61)	0.005
Cough without sputum	611/1202(0.51)	278/499(0.56)	282/592(0.48)	0.009
Dyspnea	636/1202(0.53)	291/499(0.58)	289/592(0.49)	0.002
Myalgia/Arthralgia	438/1202(0.36)	212/499(0.42)	199/592(0.34)	0.003
Diarrhea, nausea or vomiting	373/1202(0.31)	194/499(0.39)	149/592(0.25)	<0.001
On Statins	484/1202(0.40)	194/499(0.39)	251/592(0.42)	0.264
On ACE Inhibitors or ARBs	280/1202(0.23)	117/499(0.23)	141/592(0.24)	0.943
Home with self-quarantine	267/1202(0.22)	117/499(0.23)	122/592(0.21)	0.291
Admitted to hospital	715/1202(0.59)	289/499(0.58)	374/592(0.63)	0.087
Admitted to ICU	163/1202(0.14)	75/499(0.15)	62/592(0.10)	0.030
Admission labs^(‡) (Median [IQR])				
CRP (mg/L; n=1066)	73.7 (32.8,143)	78.5 (40.7,146)	67.4 (27.1,136)	0.001
ESR (mm/h; n=951)	39 (23,59)	39 (27,59)	39 (22,59)	0.194
D-Dimer (ng/mL; n=1000)	986 (643,1690)	930 (630,1600)	1040 (676,1690)	0.233
Ferritin (ug/L; n=1077)	517 (254,1030)	511 (256,952)	509 (242,1120)	0.729
WBC (K/uL; n=1110)	6.63 (5,8.85)	6.77 (5.19,8.56)	6.46 (4.9,8.95)	0.291
IL-6 (pg/mL; n=313)	27.8 (14.1,57.3)	29.6 (15,55.8)	27.8 (13.1,60)	0.646
Glucose (mg/dL; n=1107)	125 (106,163)	126 (106,164)	124 (105,161)	0.462
Peak labs (Median [IQR])				
CRP (mg/L; n=1159)	140 (66.4,250)	147 (74.2,266)	129 (60,229)	<0.001
ESR (mm/h; n=1068)	56.5 (35,103)	61 (38,109)	54 (33,98.8)	0.016
D-Dimer (ng/mL; n=1138)	1700 (901,3670)	1900 (887,4320)	1520 (916,3190)	0.047
Ferritin (ug/L; n=1164)	796 (388,1620)	788 (423,1590)	778 (344,1620)	0.45
WBC (K/uL; n=1190)	9.02 (6.76,13.5)	9.16 (6.93,13.7)	8.85 (6.45,13)	0.045
IL-6 (pg/mL; n=398)	30.8 (14.9,69.1)	31 (16.4,69.3)	30.8 (13.6,73.6)	0.788
Glucose (mg/dL; n=1179)	153 (121,228)	162 (124,236)	148 (118,217)	0.011
Complications within 28 days^(§)				
ARDS	284/1202(0.24)	141/499(0.28)	111/592(0.19)	<0.001
Liver dysfunction	227/1202(0.19)	107/499(0.21)	101/592(0.17)	0.079
Acute renal injury/failure	278/1202(0.23)	120/499(0.24)	130/592(0.22)	0.456

^(*)Obesity is defined as BMI $\geq$ 30 and was missing for 111 patients; ^(†)P-values correspond to a two-sample test of proportions (for categorical variables) or Wilcoxon rank sum tests for (numeric variables) comparing corresponding characteristic of obese versus non-obese patients; ^(‡)Admission labs recorded within +/-3 days of hospital admission; ^(§)Complications reported – Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS), liver dysfunction (as reflected by aspartate aminotransferase (AST) or alanine aminotransferase (ALT) >3 times the upper limit of normal) and acute renal injury/failure – occurred within 28 days of presentation to care.

Table S2. Causal mediation model analysis of peak CRP based on MGH Cohort

All patients	Total Effect Model Outcome: vent/death		Mediator Model Outcome: peak CRP ^(*)		Outcome model Outcome: vent/death	
	OR (95% CI)	p-value	Estimate	p-value	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Obesity	1.73 (1.25, 2.41)	p=0.001	0.261	p<0.001	1.49 (1.03, 2.16)	p=0.035
Sex (Male)	1.49 (1.09, 2.05)	p=0.013	0.171	p=0.005	1.30 (0.91, 1.85)	p=0.152
Age	1.04 (1.03, 1.05)	p<0.001	0.010	p<0.001	1.03 (1.02, 1.05)	p<0.001
Race (Black)	0.91 (0.55, 1.52)	p=0.728	0.118	p=0.256	0.82 (0.46, 1.45)	p=0.498
Race (Hispanic)	1.01 (0.68, 1.51)	p=0.943	0.274	p<0.001	0.85 (0.55, 1.33)	p=0.475
Race (Other)	1.83 (1.10, 3.03)	p=0.020	0.344	p<0.001	1.43 (0.81, 2.53)	p=0.217
# of CRPs	0.68 (0.64, 0.73)	p<0.001	0.056	p<0.001	0.61 (0.56, 0.66)	p<0.001
Peak CRP	-		-	-	1.36 (0.56, 3.29)	p=0.502
Peak CRP*Age	-		-	-	1.02 (1.00, 1.03)	p=0.013
≥ 65 yrs						
Obesity	1.45 (0.88, 2.38)	p=0.145	0.151	p=0.146	1.28 (0.72, 2.25)	p=0.399
Sex (Male)	1.91 (1.21, 3.02)	p=0.006	0.194	p=0.043	1.74 (1.04, 2.92)	p=0.035
Age	1.02 (0.99, 1.05)	p=0.146	0.007	p=0.224	1.02 (0.98, 1.05)	p=0.350
Race (Black)	1.75 (0.84, 3.64)	p=0.136	0.040	p=0.802	1.95 (0.85, 4.49)	p=0.115
Race (Hispanic)	0.99 (0.51, 1.92)	p=0.985	0.213	p=0.121	0.88 (0.43, 1.82)	p=0.729
Race (Other)	1.51 (0.76, 3.01)	p=0.239	0.239	p=0.111	1.28 (0.59, 2.78)	p=0.531
# of CRPs	0.75 (0.69, 0.81)	p<0.001	0.030	p=0.008	0.70 (0.64, 0.76)	p<0.001
Peak CRP	-	-	-	-	4.33 (2.85, 6.58)	p<0.001
<65 yrs						
Obesity	1.99 (1.26, 3.14)	p=0.004	0.325	p<0.001	1.57 (0.93, 2.64)	p=0.091
Sex (Male)	1.19 (0.76, 1.87)	p=0.445	0.134	p=0.096	0.97 (0.58, 1.62)	p=0.910
Age	1.04 (1.02, 1.06)	p<0.001	0.013	p<0.001	1.04 (1.01, 1.06)	p=0.003
Race (Black)	0.51 (0.23, 1.12)	p=0.092	0.153	p=0.274	0.41 (0.17, 0.98)	p=0.045
Race (Hispanic)	1.00 (0.58, 1.73)	p=0.986	0.291	p=0.003	0.79 (0.43, 1.48)	p=0.470
Race (Other)	2.29 (1.08, 4.87)	p=0.031	0.390	p=0.005	1.62 (0.68, 3.88)	p=0.278
# of CRPs	0.58 (0.51, 0.66)	p<0.001	0.082	p<0.001	0.49 (0.42, 0.56)	p<0.001
Peak CRP	-	-	-	-	4.51 (3.05, 6.67)	p<0.001

^(*)Peak CRP level prior to mechanical ventilation, death or hospital discharge was used. All values were natural log transformed and standardized for analysis. At most one CRP measurement per day was recorded in the data registry. In the case of multiple measurements per days, the first one was used. The median (IQR) of the number of measurements per person was 4 (2,7).

Table S3. Summary data on patients with and without complete data by cohort.

	MGH Cohort (N=1202)		CUIMC/NYP (N=2,626)	
	Complete Data ^(*) (N=996)	Incomplete Data ^(*) (N=206)	Complete Data ^(*) (N=1984)	Incomplete Data ^(*) (N=642)
Presentation to Care (PTC)				
Female sex– count/total (%)	442/996(0.44) ^(‡)	72/206(0.35) ^(‡)	818/1972(0.41) ^(‡)	311/654(0.48) ^(‡)
Age in years (Median [IQR])	60.7 (48,74.3) ^(‡)	55.5 (40.2,71.8) ^(‡)	66 (55,76)	67 (53,80)
Age ≥ 65 years	407/996(0.41)	71/205(0.35)	1054/1972(0.53)	366/654(0.56)
Smoker (ever)	387/989(0.39) ^(‡)	56/206(0.27) ^(‡)	n/a	n/a
BMI (Median [IQR])	29.1 (25.6,33.6)	31 (26.3,36.5)	28.1 (24.6,32.7)	27.5 (25,31.5)
White/non-Hispanic	407/996(0.41) ^(‡)	56/181(0.31) ^(‡)	183/1972(0.09)	54/654(0.08)
Black/non-Hispanic	112/996(0.11)	18/181(0.10)	236/1972(0.12)	84/654(0.13)
Hispanic	356/996(0.36)	79/181(0.44)	969/1972(0.49)	345/654(0.53)
Other	121/996(0.12)	28/181(0.15)	584/1972(0.30)	171/654(0.26)
Co-morbidities				
CAD/MI	160/996(0.16) ^(‡)	18/206(0.09) ^(‡)	248/1972(0.13)	81/654(0.12)
Hypertension	534/996(0.54) ^(‡)	82/206(0.40) ^(‡)	1110/1972(0.56) ^(‡)	320/654(0.49) ^(‡)
Dyslipidemia	393/996(0.39) ^(‡)	57/206(0.28) ^(‡)	n/a	n/a
Pulmonary disease history	302/993(0.30)	57/205(0.28)	n/a	n/a
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	335/996(0.34)	67/206(0.33)	771/1972(0.39) ^(‡)	197/654(0.30) ^(‡)
Outcome^(†)				
ventilation or death	296/995(0.30) ^(‡)	94/206(0.46) ^(‡)	736/1972(0.37) ^(‡)	172/654(0.26) ^(‡)
ventilation	226/996(0.23) ^(‡)	79/206(0.38) ^(‡)	509/1972(0.26) ^(‡)	50/654(0.08) ^(‡)
Death	128/995(0.13)	33/206(0.16)	462/1972(0.23)	161/654(0.25)

^(*)Complete data includes patients with no missing information on peak CRP, BMI, sex, age, race/ethnicity and outcome. Incomplete data includes patients missing information on at least one of these variables. ^(†)Outcome is composite of mechanical ventilation or death within 28 days of PTC in MGH analysis and composite of ventilation or death in 30 or more days in CUIMC/NYP analysis. ^(‡)Proportion is statistically significantly different (two-sided test of proportions p<0.05) between patients with complete data and patients with incomplete data. Note that direction of effects may vary. There is not a detectable difference between these two groups for the remaining variables at the 0.05 level.

Table S4. Clinical characteristics overall and by obesity status for CUIMC/NYP cohort

	Overall (N=2,626)	Obese^(*) (N=794)	Not Obese^(*) (N=1,319)	P-value^(†)
Hospital Admittance				
Female sex– count/total (%)	1129/2626(0.43)	401/794(0.51)	493/1319(0.37)	<0.001
Age – Median (IQR)	66 (54,77)	60 (49,71)	69 (58,79)	<0.001
Age ≥65	1420/2626(0.54)	318/794(0.40)	792/1319(0.60)	<0.001
Body Mass Index	28.02 (24.6,32.7)	34.25 (32.0,38.5)	25.40 (22.8,27.5)	<0.001
White/non-Hispanic	237/2626(0.09)	73/794(0.09)	126/1319(0.10)	0.844
Black/non-Hispanic	320/2626(0.12)	112/794(0.14)	142/1319(0.11)	0.027
Hispanic	1314/2626(0.50)	387/794(0.49)	654/1319(0.50)	0.741
Other	755/2626(0.29)	222/794(0.28)	397/1319(0.30)	0.319
Fever	604/2624 (0.23)	236/794(0.30)	270/1319(0.20)	<0.001
Statins	951/2626(0.36)	308/794(0.39)	478/1319(0.36)	0.259
ACE Inhibitors or ARBs	442/2626(0.17)	149/794(0.19)	203/1319(0.15)	0.050
CAD/MI ^(‡)	329/2626(0.13)	91/794(0.11)	170/1319(0.13)	0.369
Hypertension	1,430/2626(0.54)	454/794(0.57)	718/1319(0.54)	0.237
Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	968/2626(0.37)	314/794(0.40)	496/1319(0.38)	0.399
Admission labs				
CRP (mg/L; n = 2,414)	118 (56.8,205)	118 (59.4,199)	119 (57.3,208)	0.967
ESR (mm/hr; n =2,285)	71 (48,97)	74 (52,96)	69 (46,97)	0.080
D-Dimer (ng/ml; n = 2,176)	1505 (830,3280)	1320 (780,2940)	1620 (880,3585)	0.002
Ferritin (ng/ml; n = 2,391)	703 (345,1293)	649 (321,1175)	757 (364,1434)	0.003
WBC (K/ul; n = 2,617)	7.50 (5.5,10.1)	7.45 (5.6,10.0)	7.47 (5.6,10.3)	0.661
IL-6 (pg/ml; n = 1,480)	65.8 (28.3,145.0)	66.6 (28.3,149.2)	69.6 (29.2,147.3)	0.826
Peak labs				
CRP (mg/L; n = 2,409)	167 (83.8,281)	180 (88.9,291)	169 (87.7,290)	0.373
ESR (mm/hr; n = 2,283)	90 (62,119)	94 (67,125)	91 (62,120)	0.035
D-Dimer (ng/ml; n = 2,165)	2530 (1060,9600)	2350 (1040,12980)	2865 (1198,10293)	0.306
Ferritin (ng/ml; n = 2,388)	931 (437,1934)	922 (429,1810)	1038 (480,2110)	0.031
WBC (K/ul; n = 2,609)	11.0 (7.6,16.6)	11.2 (7.8,17.0)	11.6 (7.9,17.4)	0.612
IL-6 (pg/ml; n = 1,480)	91.2 (35.6,278.2)	96.6 (38.4,315)	101 (38.2,315)	0.852
Outcomes at 30+ days				
Ventilator or death	885/2626(0.34)	266/794(0.34)	465/1319(0.35)	0.4395
Ventilator ^(§)	522/2626(0.20)	207/794(0.26)	271/1319(0.21)	0.0039
Death	623/2626(0.24)	151/794(0.19)	324/1319(0.25)	0.0037

^(*)Obesity is defined as BMI>30 and was missing for 513 patients. ^(†)P-values correspond to a two-sample test of proportions (for categorical variables) or t-test for (numeric variables) comparing corresponding characteristic of obese versus non-obese patients. ^(‡)Diagnoses based on ICD codes in electronic health record at time of admission or during hospitalization: ICD codes included I21-25, Z95.1 and Z98.61 for Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) and Myocardial Infarction (MI), I10-13, I15-16, O10.1 and O10.9 for Hypertension and E08-11, E13 and O24.4 for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

^(§)363 patients died without being on ventilator.

Table S5. Replication analysis of peak values of biomarkers^(*) using the CUIMC/NYP cohort

	Total Effect Model^(†)	Mediator Model^(†)	Outcome Model^(†)		Proportion Mediated
	Outcome: vent/death	Outcome: biomarker	Outcome: Ventilation/death		
	OR (obesity, p)	Est (obesity, p)	OR (obesity, p)	OR (biomarker, p)	(p-value)
CRP					
All ages (n=1,972)	1.24 (p=0.037)	0.196 (p<0.001)	1.17 (p=0.167)	-(‡)	0.67 (p=0.002)
≥ 65 yrs (n=1,054)	1.16 (p=0.318)	0.120 (p=0.071)	1.07 (p=0.671)	4.21 (p<0.001)	0.63 (p=0.230)
< 65 yrs (n=918)	1.35 (p=0.042)	0.247 (p<0.001)	1.29 (p=0.133)	8.12 (p<0.001)	0.68 (p<0.001)
ESR					
All ages (n=1,867)	1.26 (p=0.028)	0.179 (p<0.001)	1.19 (p=0.119)	-(‡)	0.43 (p=0.010)
≥ 65 yrs (n=988)	1.18 (p=0.279)	0.182 (p=0.012)	1.09 (p=0.554)	1.60 (p<0.001)	0.37 (p=0.276)
< 65 yrs (n=879)	1.37 (p=0.037)	0.155 (p=0.022)	1.32 (p=0.084)	3.26 (p<0.001)	0.40 (p=0.038)
D-dimer					
(n=1,801)	1.32 (p=0.010)	0.079 (p=0.112)	1.28 (p=0.063)	-(‡)	0.31 (p=0.132)
≥ 65 yrs (n=939)	1.21 (p=0.209)	0.025 (p=0.725)	1.23 (p=0.226)	2.84 (p<0.001)	0.13 (p=0.640)
< 65 yrs (n=862)	1.44 (p=0.018)	0.100 (p=0.153)	1.39 (p=0.129)	7.73 (p<0.001)	0.39 (p=0.188)
Ferritin					
(n=1,960)	1.27 (p=0.023)	-0.015 (p=0.750)	1.41 (p=0.003)	4.42 (p<0.001)	<0.01 (p=0.768)
≥ 65 yrs (n=1,036)	1.19 (p=0.237)	-0.188 (p=0.003)	1.45 (p=0.017)	2.49 (p<0.001)	<0.01 (p=0.240)
< 65 yrs (n=924)	1.37 (p=0.037)	0.089 (p=0.187)	1.40 (p=0.044)	3.26 (p<0.001)	0.24 (p=0.200)
WBC					
(n=2,085)	1.31 (p=0.008)	0.057 (p=0.227)	1.39 (p=0.009)	-(‡)	0.22 (p=0.234)
≥ 65 yrs (n=1,093)	1.24 (p=0.134)	-0.006 (p=0.934)	1.38 (p=0.049)	3.76 (p<0.001)	0.02 (p=0.960)
< 65 yrs (n=992)	1.40 (p=0.022)	0.093 (p=0.160)	1.38 (p=0.104)	7.37 (p<0.001)	0.37 (p=0.186)
IL-6					
(n=1,240)	1.26 (p=0.063)	0.109 (p=0.073)	1.18 (p=0.296)	12.82 (p<0.001)	0.52 (p=0.100)
≥ 65 yrs (n=674)	1.18 (p=0.367)	0.088 (p=0.270)	1.14 (p=0.543)	4.95 (p<0.001)	0.43 (p=0.360)
< 65 yrs (n=566)	1.37 (p=0.076)	0.111 (p=0.227)	1.27 (p=0.298)	7.31 (p<0.001)	0.48 (p=0.230)

^(*)Peak biomarker level was determined based on all measurements before and after mechanical ventilation. All values were natural log transformed and standardized for analysis. ^(†)All models included terms for obesity and were adjusted for age, sex and race/ethnicity. The outcome model included both obesity and the biomarker as predictor variables. ^(‡)The outcome model had a significant biomarker by age interaction and therefore the main effect of the biomarker was not reported here.

Table S6. Causal mediation analysis using pre- and post-ventilation CRP levels^(*) in MGH cohort

	Total Effect Model^(†) Outcome: vent/death	Mediator Model^(†) Outcome: CRP	Outcome Model^(‡) Outcome: vent/death		Proportion Mediated
	OR (obesity, p)	Est (obesity, p)	OR (obesity, p)	OR (biomarker, p)	(p-value)
CRP					
All ages (n=1031)	1.46 (p=0.015)	0.214 (p<0.001)	1.28 (p=0.151)	7.38 (p<0.001)	0.63 (p<0.001)
≥ 65 yrs (n=418)	1.23 (p=0.354)	0.137 (p=0.154)	1.03 (p=0.025)	10.99 (p<0.001)	0.76 (p=0.260)
< 65 yrs (n=613)	1.71 (p=0.022)	0.235 (p=0.001)	1.57 (p=0.069)	5.52 (p<0.001)	0.47 (p=0.004)

^(*)Peak CRP was determined using both pre and post-ventilation, similar to the CUIMC/NYP cohort. All values were natural log transformed and standardized for analysis. ^(†)All models included terms for obesity and were adjusted for age, sex, race/ethnicity and number of biomarker measurements. The outcome model included both obesity and the biomarker as predictor variables. ^(‡)Model for CRP had significant CRP by age interaction and therefore main effect was not reported here.

Figure S1. Causal mediation modeling estimates by biomarker and age category.

*The OR corresponding to CRP in the outcome model is not presented in this figure as the CRP by age interaction term was significant and therefore the main effect of CRP cannot be interpreted independently.

The figure includes effect estimates of obesity on biomarker levels based on the mediator model (top panel) and the odds ratios (ORs) of biomarker levels on mechanical ventilation or death based on the outcome model (bottom panel). Estimates and corresponding 95% confidence intervals are illustrated for each biomarker overall and stratified by age. Dashed horizontal lines correspond to the null of no effect.